

A study on partial molar volumes of some mineral salts in water at various temperatures

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Partial molar volumes of some mineral salts, viz. sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate, ammonium sulfate, magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in water have been determined from solution density measurements at various temperatures and mineral salt concentrations. The data are evaluated by using Masson equation and the obtained parameters are interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. Sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and ammonium sulfate have been found to act as the structure-breakers whereas magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate act as structure makers/promoters in water.

Partial molar volumes of electrolytes provide valuable information about the ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions^{1,2}. This information is of fundamental importance for understanding the reaction rates and equilibria involving dissolved electrolytes. Survey of literature showed that although many studies on thermodynamic properties of various electrolytes have been carried out in single component and in mixed solvent systems, but a little attention has been paid to the behavior of mineral salts in water or any other solvent. The present mineral salts have been selected for the study because they are important constituents³ of biofluids and soil fluids. The main ionic solutes in biofluids are the alkali cations, viz. Na⁺ and K⁺ with Mg²⁺ in small amount, the common anions are the small amount of SO₄²⁻ and HPO₄²⁻. These ionic solutes have two most outstanding functions: (i) they are normally responsible for the osmotic pressure of biofluids, and (ii) two ions Na⁺ and K⁺ are mainly responsible for the striking difference in the composition of extracellular and intracellular fluids of soil and sap fluids in plants.

As partial molar volume of a solute reflects the cumulative effects⁴ of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions, it would be of interest to study partial molar volume of some strong electrolytes. Such data are expected to highlight the role of the cation and of the anion of an electrolyte in influencing its partial molar volume at infinite dilutions in water. These considerations prompted us to undertake the present study.

Results and Discussion

The densities measured for the solutions of the salts in water at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K, have been used to calcu-

late the apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) of the electrolytes. The plots of ϕ_v against square-root of molar concentration ($c^{1/2}$) were found to be linear with positive slopes for the sulfates of sodium, potassium and magnesium, while the slopes were found to be negative for ammonium sulfate and phosphates of ammonium, sodium and potassium.

The limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) were calculated using the least-square treatment to the plots of ϕ_v vs $c^{1/2}$, using Masson's equation⁵,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v c^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_v^0 is the partial molar volume at infinite dilution and S_v the experimental slope. The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v along with standard errors are listed in Table 1. It is evident from the data that S_v is positive and large for sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and magnesium sulphate in water at different temperatures. Since S_v is a measure of solute-solute/ion-ion interactions, the results indicate the presence of very strong ion-ion interactions. These interactions, however, decrease with the increase in temperature in case of sodium sulfate and potassium sulfate which may be attributed to the increase in solvation of ions with the rise in temperature. In case of magnesium sulfate, however, they increase with the increase in temperature which may be attributed to the decrease in solvation of ions with the rise in temperature.

These results of sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and magnesium sulfate at different temperatures suggest a possible explanation for the absence of the negative S_v values for all the three salts in water. Although at infinite dilution all these salts are completely dissociated in water at different temperatures; the situation would be different at higher

Table 1. Partial molar volume (ϕ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v) for the mineral salts in water at various temperatures*

Temp. K	ϕ_v^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	S_v $(\text{cm}^3 \text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2})$
	Sodium sulfate	
303	12.41 (0.49)	15.77 (0.80)
308	14.70 (0.33)	11.88 (0.65)
313	15.65 (0.52)	9.60 (0.84)
318	15.99 (0.04)	9.69 (0.19)
	Potassium sulfate	
303	32.87 (1.79)	13.55 (1.79)
308	34.06 (0.18)	11.50 (0.67)
313	34.98 (0.12)	10.36 (0.47)
318	35.77 (0.09)	8.60 (0.35)
	Ammonium sulfate	
303	55.41 (0.51)	-4.98 (0.15)
308	55.71 (0.04)	-4.27 (0.16)
313	55.98 (0.24)	-4.50 (0.81)
318	56.71 (0.05)	-6.19 (0.21)
	Magnesium sulfate	
303	123.41 (0.89)	20.64 (3.38)
308	94.56 (1.24)	79.41 (4.72)
313	52.81 (4.91)	203.88 (1.75)
318	25.83 (1.39)	271.35 (5.30)
	Diammonium hydrogen phosphate	
303	101.29 (0.17)	-141.12 (0.81)
308	86.64 (0.87)	-86.01 (1.71)
313	79.95 (1.18)	-72.49 (2.34)
318	74.34 (0.81)	-61.65 (1.61)
	Sodium dihydrogen phosphate	
303	141.33 (1.71)	-221.13 (2.33)
308	137.24 (0.22)	-210.32 (4.37)
313	114.57 (2.51)	-108.33 (2.90)
318	88.36 (1.05)	-43.40 (2.07)
	Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate	
303	106.16 (0.53)	-174.42 (1.05)
308	90.60 (0.17)	-116.43 (0.34)
313	55.96 (0.55)	-20.16 (1.09)
318	49.77 (0.43)	-10.33 (0.85)

*Standard errors in parenthesis.

concentrations. These salts are not completely ionized such that interionic penetration does not occur which may give rise to positive slope in the ϕ_v vs $c^{1/2}$ curves.

It is also clear from Table 1 that S_v is negative for ammonium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in water at different temperatures. The results indicate the

presence of weak ion-ion interactions. These interactions, however, increase with the increase of temperature, which may be attributed to the decrease in solvation of ions with the rise in temperature. Further, in water, these salts may be completely ionized at fairly high concentrations. Therefore, appreciable interionic penetration occurs and this gives rise to a negative slope in the ϕ_v vs $c^{1/2}$ curves for these mineral salts.

Since ϕ_v^0 is a measure of ion-solvent interactions (as ion-ion interactions vanish at infinite dilution), therefore, it is evident from Table 1 that the values of ϕ_v^0 are positive and large for all the mineral salts in water at different temperatures, indicating the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions. These interactions are further strengthened with the rise in temperature, in case of sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and ammonium sulfate. The increase in ϕ_v^0 with the increase in temperature, for individual mineral salt, may be attributed to increase in solvation. But in case of magnesium sulfate, these interactions, however, decrease with the rise in temperature which may be attributed to the decrease in solvation.

Since, the sulfate ion is common ion in case of these mineral salts so from the values of ϕ_v^0 at a particular temperature, it may be concluded that the solvation of cations in water follows the order : $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Na}^+$. Further, the sharp decrease in ϕ_v^0 , in going from lower to higher temperature in case of diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, results in the decrease in ion-solvent interactions which may be attributed to the decrease in ion-solvation in water.

The temperature dependence of ϕ_v^0 for various mineral salts, studied here, in water, can be expressed by the general equation (eq. 2),

$$\phi_v^0 = a + bT = cT^2 \quad (2)$$

Various coefficients of eq. (2) for different salts are given in Table 2. The partial molar expansibilities, $\phi_E^0 = (\partial\phi_v^0/\partial T)$ calculated from general eq. (2) are given in Table 3. It is

Table 2. Various coefficients of eq. (2) for different salts

Salt	a	b	c
Na_2SO_4	-2627.45	16.83	-0.027
K_2SO_4	-543.19	3.54	-0.005
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	-18.76	0.43	-0.001
$\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4045.73	-18.90	0.019
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$	14334	-90.01	0.152
$\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5544	-34.88	0.056
K_2HPO_4	4256	-24.97	0.037

evident from Table 3 that ϕ_E^0 decreases in magnitude with the increase in temperature for sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and ammonium sulfate in water, indicating thereby that the behavior of these salts is just like common salts, because in the case of common salts the molar expansibility should decrease with the increases in temperature^{6,7}. It is also evident from Table 3 that the value of ϕ_E^0 increases in magnitude with the increase in temperature for magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in water. The increase in magnitude is positive indicating thereby that the behavior of these salts is similar to that of symmetrical tetraalkylammonium salts⁸.

Table 3. Partial molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) for the mineral salts in water at different temperatures

Salt	Partial molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) ml/(mol) (K)			
	303	308	313	318 K
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.471	0.201	-0.069	-0.339
K ₂ SO ₄	0.265	0.211	0.157	0.103
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.063	0.062	0.051	0.045
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	-6.958	-6.761	-6.564	-6.367
(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	-3.955	-2.535	-1.115	0.305
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	-0.943	-0.383	0.177	0.737
K ₂ HPO ₄	-2.543	-2.173	-1.803	-1.433

The decrease in ϕ_E^0 with the increase in temperature for sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and ammonium sulfate in water, shows the absence of caging or packing effect^{7,8}. On the other hand, the positive increase in ϕ_E^0 with increase in temperature for magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in water, may be ascribed to 'caging effect'^{7,8}.

During past few years it has been emphasized by different workers that S_v is not the sole criterion for determining the structure-making or -breaking nature of any solute. Hepler⁹ developed a technique of examining the sign of $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$ for various solutes in terms of long range structure-making and -breaking capacity of the solutes in aqueous solutions using the general thermodynamic expression,

$$[\partial c_p / \partial P]_T = -[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p \quad (3)$$

On the basis of this expression it has been deduced that structure-making solute should have positive value, whereas structure-breaking solute negative value. In the present system, it is observed from eq. (2) that $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$ is negative for sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate and ammonium

sulfate in water, which means that these mineral salts behave as structure-breakers.

On the other hand, the value of $[\partial^2 \phi_v^0 / \partial T^2]_p$ is positive for magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, suggesting thereby that these mineral salts act as structure-makers/promoters in water.

Experimental

Sodium sulfate, potassium sulfate, ammonium sulfate, magnesium sulfate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (all A.R.) were used after drying over P₂O₅ in a desiccator. Double-distilled water (specific conductivity of the order of 10⁻⁶ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) was always prepared afresh.

All the solutions of electrolytes were made by weight and conversion of molality (m) into molar concentration (c) was done by using the standard expression¹⁰, $c = 1000 dm / (1000 + mM_2)$, where d is the solution density and M_2 the molecular weight of the electrolyte. Density was measured by an apparatus of the Ward and Millero¹ type described elsewhere¹² and temperature was kept within ±0.01°. Accuracy in the density measurement was ±0.000011 g m⁻³. The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density data using the standard expression¹³, $\phi_v = M_2 / d_0 - 1000 (d - d_0) / d_0 c$, where d_0 is the solvent density.

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